

BELMONT
FORUM

FAPESP
FUNDAÇÃO DE AMPARO À PESQUISA
DO ESTADO DE SÃO PAULO

AGENCE NATIONALE DE LA RECHERCHE
ANR

PARSEC

Mapping the socio-economic consequences of PAs in west coast USA

E. Jamie Trammell, Southern Oregon University

Jeffrey Evans, The Nature Conservancy

Jesse Jo Rego, Southern Oregon University

Alec Bayarsky, Southern Oregon University

ENVIRONMENTAL
SCIENCE & POLICY
SOUTHERN OREGON UNIVERSITY

The Nature
Conservancy

Research Hypotheses

Research Design

- First, explore what quantitative (not qualitative) relationships, if any, between the socioeconomic conditions surrounding/including PAs
- Second, explore if these differ spatially
- Third, explore whether socioeconomic relationships vary by ecoregion

Protected Areas in U.S.

Proportion of Protected Lands by Ecoregion (Level 1)

Socioeconomic Measures

U.S. Census data

- Formal census every 10 years
- Subsampled annually
- Hierarchical spatial organization
 - Finest spatial scale called “Census Tract”
 - Census Block more available
 - Sub-county for some variables
- Indicators Chosen:
 - Median Income
 - Poverty
 - Educational Attainment
 - Total Population
 - Gini Index
 - Resource Intensive Employment
 - Fish/Ag/Forestry
 - Recreation

Oregon as a Test Case

- Oregon has diversity
 - Wide range of ecoregions
 - Diverse mix of socioeconomic conditions
 - Many rural communities
 - Plenty of protected areas
- Most PAs in the U.S. are on the west coast
 - Nearly 1,000 IUCN I, II, III in Oregon

Statewide vs. Protected Areas Total Population

Statewide vs. Protected Areas Recreation Jobs

Median Income near PAs

Own_Name	Median Income	Percent Below Poverty	Gini	Total Population	Percent Bachelors +	Ag, Forestry, Fishing Jobs	Recreation Jobs
REG	\$ 81,324	9%	0.44	99,974	36%	685	4,509
CITY	\$ 68,314	12%	0.45	151,000	40%	957	7,792
CNTY	\$ 61,399	14%	0.45	47,717	37%	633	2,505
OTHS	\$ 59,789	13%	0.45	110,056	24%	1,297	5,378
USFS	\$ 58,382	1%	0.27	1,046	3%	15	40
FWS	\$ 54,679	11%	0.40	2,648	22%	127	116
OTHF	\$ 54,098	19%	0.42	38,181	16%	1,996	803
DESG	\$ 53,425	15%	0.43	3,092	20%	131	128
SFW	\$ 53,240	13%	0.43	11,128	22%	210	534
SPR	\$ 52,342	15%	0.44	11,790	24%	168	605
UNKL	\$ 51,572	19%	0.47	269,879	34%	1,845	14,300
NGO	\$ 51,332	14%	0.42	5,579	18%	103	266
PVT	\$ 49,724	15%	0.42	7,319	22%	178	298
UNK	\$ 48,963	12%	0.40	3,623	15%	114	108
NPS	\$ 47,260	14%	0.39	3,261	13%	153	77
SDOL	\$ 46,096	16%	0.47	19,494	19%	276	1,133
SDNR	\$ 45,952	16%	0.39	3,286	13%	173	76
Ave	\$ 55,170	13%	0.42	46,416	22%	533	2,275

Population near PAs

Own_Name	Median Income	Percent Below Poverty	Gini	Total Population	Percent Bachelors +	Ag, Forestry, Fishing Jobs	Recreation Jobs
UNKL	\$ 51,572	19%	0.47	269,879	34%	1,845	14,300
CITY	\$ 68,314	12%	0.45	151,000	40%	957	7,792
OTHS	\$ 59,789	13%	0.45	110,056	24%	1,297	5,378
REG	\$ 81,324	9%	0.44	99,974	36%	685	4,509
CNTY	\$ 61,399	14%	0.45	47,717	37%	633	2,505
Ave	\$ 64,479	13%	0.45	135,725	34%	1,084	6,897
SDOL	\$ 46,096	16%	0.47	19,494	19%	276	1,133
OTHF	\$ 54,098	19%	0.42	38,181	16%	1,996	803
SPR	\$ 52,342	15%	0.44	11,790	24%	168	605
SFW	\$ 53,240	13%	0.43	11,128	22%	210	534
PVT	\$ 49,724	15%	0.42	7,319	22%	178	298
NGO	\$ 51,332	14%	0.42	5,579	18%	103	266
DESG	\$ 53,425	15%	0.43	3,092	20%	131	128
FWS	\$ 54,679	11%	0.40	2,648	22%	127	116
UNK	\$ 48,963	12%	0.40	3,623	15%	114	108
NPS	\$ 47,260	14%	0.39	3,261	13%	153	77
SDNR	\$ 45,952	16%	0.39	3,286	13%	173	76
USFS	\$ 58,382	1%	0.27	1,046	3%	15	40

Spatial Heterogeneity

Spatial Heterogeneity Fusion

- We have ecoregions
 - Nested, based on a range of physical environmental variables
- Does our relationship to protected areas depend on the physical environment?
- Are their nested relationships between socioeconomic variables and ecoregional data?
- Unified Manifold Approximation & Projection (UMAP)
 - Non-linear dimension reduction
 - Honors spatial relationships
 - Can be mapped back to real space

UMAP Clusters

UMAP Clusters

realm

- Cool Temperate Dry Cropland on Hills
- Cool Temperate Dry Cropland on Mountains
- Cool Temperate Dry Cropland on Plains
- Cool Temperate Dry Cropland on Tablelands
- Cool Temperate Dry Forest on Mountains
- Cool Temperate Dry Shrubland on Mountains
- Cool Temperate Dry Shrubland on Plains
- Cool Temperate Dry Shrubland on Tablelands
- Cool Temperate Moist Forest on Mountains
- Warm Temperate Dry Cropland on Hills
- Warm Temperate Dry Cropland on Mountains
- Warm Temperate Dry Cropland on Plains
- Warm Temperate Dry Cropland on Tablelands
- Warm Temperate Dry Forest on Mountains
- Warm Temperate Moist Cropland on Hills
- Warm Temperate Moist Cropland on Mountains
- Warm Temperate Moist Cropland on Plains
- Warm Temperate Moist Forest on Hills
- Warm Temperate Moist Forest on Mountains
- Warm Temperate Moist Settlement on Hills
- Warm Temperate Moist Settlement on Mountains

UMAP Clusters

Partial Dependence Plots

% High School Graduates

Cluster 1

Cluster 5

Partial Dependence Plots

Population over 25 years old

Cluster 1

Cluster 5

Socioeconomic Interpretation (Cluster 7)

Areas with low income, low levels of education, and a mixture of cool moist forests and dry shrublands.

Socioeconomic Interpretation (Cluster 10)

Areas with higher income, highly populated, with lots of natural resource jobs in croplands

Socioeconomic Interpretation (Cluster 9)

Areas with higher income, but in small communities throughout the cool and warm moist forests.

Next Steps

- Remap UMAP clusters using hexagons
 - Proportionality of ecological land unit, and PCA-collapsed socioeconomic variables
- Expand to Washington and Idaho (Pacific Northwest)
- Test effects of PAs *within* clusters
 - Strata for testing all three hypotheses

PARSEC is a project sponsored by the Belmont Forum as part of its Collaborative Research Action (CRA) on Science-Driven e-Infrastructures Innovation (SEI), with funding from FAPESP, the ANR, JST and the NSF, with collaborators from Australia, and support from the synthesis centre CESAB of the French Foundation for Research on Biodiversity.

We acknowledge the Traditional Owners and Custodians of the land and sea in all nations. We honour their profound connections to land, water, biodiversity and culture and pay our respects to their Elders past, present and emerging.

Inter-University Research Institute Corporation
National Institutes for the Humanities
**Research Institute for
Humanity and Nature**

**TOKYO
METROPOLITAN
UNIVERSITY**

**THE UNIVERSITY
OF QUEENSLAND
AUSTRALIA**